

Preliminary studies on pollen grain germination and pollen tube growth in crosses of *Oryza sativa* and *Porteresia coarctata*

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P. coarctata, a tetraploid species of the tribe Oryzaceae that grows in brackish water around the Bay of Bengal, is a potential source of salt tolerance genes for rice improvement. We investigated pollen grain germination and pollen tube growth in crosses of *O. sativa* and *P. coarctata* (IRGC Acc. 100124).

Initially IR56 was pollinated with *P. coarctata* and 30 ovaries examined 24 h after pollination using the aniline blue fluorescence technique.

Pollen grain germination was variable, with a mean of 68%. Pollen tube growth ceased on the stigma surface in 12 (48%) of the 25 ovaries in which pollen grain germination occurred. In the remaining ovaries (52%), pollen tubes penetrated the stigma and grew as far as the base of the style.

In a reciprocal cross, *P. coarctata* was pollinated with IR36 and IR37721, and pollinated panicles covered with glassine or polythene crossing bags. Thirty ovaries were examined for each combination. Percentage data were transformed to angles for analysis.

There were no significant differences between pollinators or crossing bags in pollen grain germination or percentage of pollen

Table 1. Mean percentage of pollen grain germination and mean percentage of pollen tubes reaching the style 24 h after pollination in crosses of *P. coarctata* with cultivars IR36 and IR37721, covered with a glassine or polythene bag. IIRRI, 1989.

Treatment	Pollen grain germination (%)	Pollen tubes reaching the style ^a (%)
Pollinator		
IR36	97.1 (84.9)	33.6 (34.8)
IR37721	96.8 (86.7)	40.7 (34.4)
Crossing bag		
Polythene	95.4 (85.2)	39.3 (40.7)
Glassine	98.4 (86.4)	35.0 (36.5)
LSD (0.05) for comparing transformed treatment means		
	20.4	37.9

^aAv of 2 replications; transformed means (angles) in parentheses.

tubes reaching the style (Table 1). Pollen tubes penetrated the stigma in all ovaries examined.

A contingency χ^2 analysis was made of the number of ovaries in which pollen tube growth ceased at the stigma surface (P1), within the stigma/style (P2), within the ovary (P3), or at the micropyle (P4) (Table 2). Pollen tube growth differed significantly among treatment combinations ($\chi^2 = 9.167$, 3 d.f., $p < 0.05$). In IR36, panicles covered by glassine bags showed greater pollen tube penetration than those covered by polythene bags. In IR37721, pollen tube growth was the same in panicles covered by glassine and polythene bags. In general, IR36 pollen tubes grew significantly further than those of IR37721 ($\chi^2 = 7.500$, 1 d.f., $p < 0.01$), reaching the ovary in

Table 2. Variation in the extent of pollen tube growth 24 h after pollination in crosses of *P. coarctata* with cultivars IR36 and IR37721, covered with a glassine or polythene bag. IIRRI, 1989.

Pollinator	Crossing bag ^a	Ovaries ^b (%)	
		P2	P3
IR36	polythene	17	83
	glassine	3	97
IR37721	polythene	30	70
	glassine	30	70

^aOvaries examined numbered 30/treatment. ^bExpressed as the percentage of ovaries in which pollen tube growth ceased at P2 = stigma/style and P3 = ovary. Values for P1 = stigma surface and P4 = micropyle were zero.

90% of the IR36 ovaries examined and 70% of the IR37721 ovaries. The type of crossing bag used had no significant effect on pollen tube growth ($\chi^2 = 0.833$, 1 d.f.).

Crosses of *O. sativa* with *P. coarctata* are inhibited by strong prefertilization incompatibility barriers. With *O. sativa* as the female parent, barriers operate to inhibit pollen tube penetration of the stigma and growth within the stigma and style. With *P. coarctata* as the female parent, pollen tube growth proceeds as far as the ovary.

Methods to overcome these incompatibility mechanisms must be identified before *O. sativa/P. coarctata* hybrids can be developed. Possible approaches include mentor pollen technique, application of hormones to stimulate pollen tube growth, and intra-ovarian pollination. □

Prefertilization incompatibility barriers in interspecific and intergeneric crosses involving *Oryza sativa*

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We studied prefertilization incompatibility barriers in selected interspecific and intergeneric crosses involving *O. sativa*.

We crossed *O. sativa* (AA) cultivar IR31917-45-3-2 with wild

species--*O. officinalis* (CC), *O. eichingeri* (CC), *O. minuta* (BBCC), *O. alta* (CCDD), *O. brachyantha* (FF), and *Rhynchoryza subulata* -- (8 replications per cross) and examined 30 ovaries in each replication. At 24 h after pollination, ovaries were fixed in 3:1 alcohol:glacial acetic acid, macerated in 8N NaOH for 2 h, stained with 0.05% toluidine blue for 10 min, and stained overnight with 0.1% aniline blue (water soluble) in 0.1N K₃PO₄. They were then mounted in glycerol and examined under ultraviolet

illumination, using a 320-400 nm exciter filter and a 470 nm barrier filter. All percentage data were transformed to angles for analysis.

A highly significant difference ($p < 0.001$) in percentage pollen grain germination was detected among pollinators (see table). Germination was significantly lower in the *R. subulata* crosses.

A contingency χ^2 analysis was made of the number of ovaries in which pollen tube growth ceased at the stigma surface, within the stigma/style, within